

Studies on the Reaction of Silver Nitrate with Organic Sulphides.

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The interaction of organic sulphides on gold chloride has been systematically studied and compounds of the type $\text{AuCl}_3 \cdot \text{R}_2\text{S}$ and $\text{AuCl} \cdot \text{R}_2\text{S}$ (where R is an alkyl radicle) have been obtained (Phillips, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1901, 23, 257; Rây and Sen, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 7, 67). From the fact that silver occurs with gold in the same group of the periodic table, it was expected that salts of silver might also interact with organic sulphides giving rise to compounds similar to those of monovalent gold. In fact, compounds of the types $\text{AgNO}_3 \cdot \text{R}_2\text{S}$ and $\text{AgNO}_3 \cdot \text{R}_2\text{S}_2$ have actually been obtained as a result of the interaction of alkyl sulphides and disulphides with silver nitrate. A compound of the formula $3\text{AgNO}_3 \cdot 2(\text{C}_3\text{H}_5)_2\text{S}$ has also been obtained as a result of the interaction of allyl sulphide with silver nitrate. By the action of mercuric chloride on the above silver salts, some interesting mercury compounds have also been obtained.

The following compounds have been prepared as a result of these reactions :

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| 1. $\text{AgNO}_3 \cdot (\text{CH}_3)_2\text{S}$. | 8. $\text{AgNO}_3 \cdot (\text{C}_7\text{H}_7)_2\text{S}_2$. |
| 2. $\text{AgNO}_3 \cdot (\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_2\text{S}$. | 9. $\text{AgNO}_3 \cdot \text{S} \begin{cases} \text{CH}_3 \\ \text{C}_2\text{H}_5 \end{cases}$. |
| 3. $\text{AgNO}_3 \cdot (\text{C}_3\text{H}_7)_2\text{S}$. | 10. $3\text{AgNO}_3 \cdot 2(\text{C}_3\text{H}_5)_2\text{S}$. |
| 4. $\text{AgNO}_3 \cdot (\text{C}_4\text{H}_9)_2\text{S}$. | 11. $\text{Hg}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 2(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{S}$. |
| 5. $\text{AgNO}_3 \cdot (\text{C}_7\text{H}_7)_2\text{S}$. | 12. $\text{HgCl}(\text{NO}_3) \cdot (\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_2\text{S}$. |
| 6. $\text{AgNO}_3 \cdot (\text{CH}_3)_2\text{S}_2$. | 13. $\text{HgCl}(\text{NO}_3) \cdot (\text{C}_4\text{H}_9)_2\text{S}$. |
| 7. $\text{AgNO}_3 \cdot (\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_2\text{S}_2$. | |

These silver compounds were found to be binary electrolytes from their conductivity data. The silver ion can be precipitated as silver chloride from the solution of the salts by means of hydrochloric acid. With potassium ferrocyanide and potassium chromate they give the respective silver compounds as with silver nitrate. These reactions

show that these compounds are either imperfect complexes or molecular compounds, the alkyl sulphide groups being loosely attached to the silver nitrate molecule. This is also confirmed from the interaction of the bases like ammonia and pyridine upon these silver salts, when the loosely attached alkyl sulphide molecules are replaced by the bases. The mercury compounds are most probably formed as follows:

1. $2 \text{AgNO}_3 \cdot (\text{CH}_3)_2\text{S} + \text{HgCl}_2 = 2 \text{AgCl} + 2(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{S} + \text{Hg}(\text{NO}_3)_2$.
 $\text{Hg}(\text{NO}_3)_2 + 2(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{S} = \text{Hg}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 2(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{S}$.
2. $\text{AgNO}_3 \cdot (\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_2\text{S} + \text{HgCl}_2 = \text{HgClNO}_3 \cdot (\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_2\text{S} + \text{AgCl}$.

It will be found that one molecule of a mono- or a disulphide combines with one molecule of silver nitrate. But in the case of allyl sulphide, which is the only unsaturated sulphide dealt with, two molecules combine with three molecules of silver nitrate. The monosulphide compounds of silver have definite melting points but disulphide compounds decompose on melting. The melting points of the compounds as well as the solubilities in water and alcohol show a marked gradation of properties. The former diminish as we pass from methyl to butyl sulphide. The solubility of the salts in water decreases as we ascend the series and the same thing takes place in alcohol as we descend the series, *i.e.*, from butyl to methyl sulphide. The compounds are very unstable. They decompose when exposed to light and moisture. The decomposition of the disulphide compounds is very rapid.

The mercury compounds are white crystals with definite melting points. They are soluble in many organic solvents as well as in water and can be crystallised from cold alcohol.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Preparation of $\text{AgNO}_3 \cdot (\text{CH}_3)_2\text{S}$.—Methyl sulphide was added to a concentrated solution of silver nitrate. After some time crystals of the compound separated out. It was crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 126° (Found: Ag, 46.71; NO_3 , 26.08; C, 10.34. $\text{AgNO}_3 \cdot (\text{CH}_3)_2\text{S}$ requires Ag, 46.55; NO_3 , 26.72; C, 10.34 per cent.).

Preparation of $\text{AgNO}_3 \cdot 2 \text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N}$ (Jørgensen, *J. pr. Chem.*, 1886, ii, 33, 501). Nearly 2 g. of the substance $\text{AgNO}_3 \cdot (\text{CH}_3)_2\text{S}$ were dissolved in 6–8 c.c. of pyridine, filtered and treated with ether. While stirring, crystals of $\text{AgNO}_3 \cdot 2\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N}$ separated out. (Found:

Ag, 32.60; N, 12.80. $\text{AgNO}_3 \cdot 2\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N}$ requires Ag, 32.92; N, 12.80 per cent.).

Preparation of $\text{AgNO}_3 \cdot (\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_2\text{S}$.—As above, to a concentrated solution of silver nitrate, ethyl sulphide was added drop by drop. The liquid was stirred, crystals separated out with evolution of heat and were recrystallised from alcohol, m.p. 112°. (Found: Ag, 41.91; NO_3 , 23.42; C, 18.89. $\text{AgNO}_3 \cdot (\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_2\text{S}$ requires Ag, 41.53; NO_3 , 23.84; C, 18.5 per cent.). Molar conductivity at infinite dilution in water was found to be 116 r.o.

Preparation of $\text{AgNO}_3 \cdot (\text{C}_3\text{H}_7)_2\text{S}$.—Propyl sulphide was added to a solution of silver nitrate. It was cooled and stirred, crystals separated out and was recrystallised from alcohol, m.p. 109°. (Found: Ag, 37.35; NO_3 , 21.51; C, 24.737. $\text{AgNO}_3 \cdot (\text{C}_3\text{H}_7)_2\text{S}$ requires Ag, 37.50; NO_3 , 21.53; C, 25.00 per cent.).

Preparation of $\text{AgNO}_3 \cdot (\text{C}_4\text{H}_9)_2\text{S}$.—This compound can be prepared as before by adding butyl sulphide to a solution of silver nitrate. The substance was also crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 98°. (Found: Ag, 34.36; NO_3 , 19.25; C, 30.01. $\text{AgNO}_3 \cdot (\text{C}_4\text{H}_9)_2\text{S}$ requires Ag, 34.17; NO_3 , 19.62; C, 30.88 per cent.).

Silver nitrate ammonia, $\text{AgNO}_3 \cdot 2\text{NH}_3$; (Wetzlar, "Hofmann's Lexicon", Vol. I (i), p. 906). About 1—2 g. of the compound $\text{AgNO}_3 \cdot (\text{C}_4\text{H}_9)_2\text{S}$ were treated with freshly prepared alcoholic ammonia. The mixture was warmed for some time and allowed to cool. Crystals of $\text{AgNO}_3 \cdot 2\text{NH}_3$ separated out. It was washed with alcohol and dried. (Found: Ag, 52.25; N, 19.81. $\text{AgNO}_3 \cdot 2\text{NH}_3$ requires Ag, 52.94; N, 20.58 per cent.).

Preparation of $\text{AgNO}_3 \cdot (\text{C}_7\text{H}_7)_2\text{S}$.—An alcoholic solution of the sulphide was added to an aqueous solution of silver nitrate. The compound $\text{AgNO}_3 \cdot (\text{C}_7\text{H}_7)_2\text{S}$ together with benzyl sulphide separated. The mixture was fractionally crystallised from alcohol two or three times and washed several times with ether in which benzyl sulphide is highly soluble and $\text{AgNO}_3 \cdot (\text{C}_7\text{H}_7)_2\text{S}$ is only moderately soluble, m.p. 93—95°. (Found: Ag, 28.02; NO_3 , 15.28; C, 43.44. $\text{AgNO}_3 \cdot (\text{C}_7\text{H}_7)_2\text{S}$ requires Ag, 28.12; NO_3 , 16.14; C, 43.76 per cent.).

Preparation of $\text{AgNO}_3 \cdot (\text{CH}_3)_2\text{S}_2$.—As we pass from mono- to disulphide the reaction takes a violent form. Reactions of this kind must be carried out at a low temperature. The silver nitrate solution was cooled in a freezing mixture for some time and the disulphide was added gradually. The crystals formed were filtered

and recrystallised from alcohol at 0°. It decomposes explosively. (Found: Ag, 40.72; NO₃, 23.14; C, 8.97. AgNO₃·(CH₃)₂S₂ requires Ag, 40.91; NO₃, 23.43; C, 9.09 per cent.).

Preparation of AgNO₃·(C₂H₅)₂S₂.—This compound was prepared by the above process. (Found: Ag, 37.32; C, 16.16. AgNO₃·(C₂H₅)₂S₂ requires Ag, 36.98; C, 16.44 per cent.).

Preparation of AgNO₃·(C₇H₇)₂S₂.—An alcoholic solution of dibenzyl disulphide was added to a concentrated solution of silver nitrate. Mixtures of AgNO₃·(C₇H₇)₂S₂ and the disulphide were formed. The latter being soluble in alcohol was removed and the former was crystallised out, m.p. 103°. (Found: Ag, 25.57; C, 44.05. AgNO₃·(C₇H₇)₂S₂ requires Ag, 25.95; C, 40.38 per cent.).

Preparation of AgNO₃·(CH₃·C₂H₅)S.—This reaction was started by the action of the sulphide upon finely powdered silver nitrate. The mixture was stirred intimately. It was placed in the dark overnight. The mass swelled up and was crystallised from alcohol. (Found: Ag, 44.25; C, 14.35. AgNO₃·(CH₃·C₂H₅)S requires Ag, 43.90; C, 14.63 per cent.).

Preparation of 3 AgNO₃·2(C₃H₅)₂S.—To a cooled concentrated solution of silver nitrate the sulphide was added gradually and stirred. The crystals separated out. It is slightly soluble in alcohol, m. p. 152°. (Found: Ag, 44.29; C, 19.36; S, 8.32. 3AgNO₃·2(C₃H₅)₂S requires Ag, 43.90; C, 19.51; S, 8.67 per cent.).

Preparation of Hg(NO₃)₂·2(CH₃)₂S.—AgNO₃·(CH₃)₂S was dissolved in alcohol. To this solution, calculated amount of mercuric chloride in alcohol was added. Silver chloride separated out. It was allowed to settle and filtered. To the filtrate ether was added when the above mentioned compound precipitated out. (Found: Hg, 44.14; N, 6.0; C, 10.39. Hg(NO₃)₂·2(CH₃)₂S requires Hg, 44.64; N, 6.25; C, 10.71 per cent.).

Preparation of HgClNO₃·(C₂H₅)₂S, HgClNO₃·(C₃H₇)₂S and HgClNO₃·(C₄H₉)₂S.—To the alcoholic solutions of AgNO₃·(C₂H₅)₂S, AgNO₃·(C₃H₇)₂S and AgNO₃·(C₄H₉)₂S, excess of mercuric chloride in alcohol was added separately. In each case silver chloride together with a white compound separated out. To the filtrate ether was added and the compound that separated out was filtered and dried. The silver chloride admixture was warmed with alcohol and filtered. The filtrate deposited beautiful crystals. The melting points of

the two fractions *viz.*, (1) obtained from ether and (2) obtained from alcohol were identical. $\text{HgClNO}_3 \cdot (\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_2\text{S}$ melts at 110° . (Found: Hg, 51.54 ; C, 12.29 ; Cl, 9.16. $\text{HgClNO}_3 \cdot (\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_2\text{S}$ requires Hg, 51.61 ; C, 12.39 ; Cl, 9.16 per cent.).

The conductivity of the compound $\text{HgCl}(\text{NO}_3) \cdot (\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_2\text{S}$ was determined by dissolving 0.7896 g. of the substance in 100 c.c. of water at 31° . The solution was then successively diluted twice, thrice and four times and the conductivity of each determined. 1, 2, 3, 4 respectively represent these solutions.

Solution.	Molar conductivity r.o.	Conc. of electrolyte mole/litre.
1	83.08	.0203
2	88.16	.00507
3	97.52	.00253
4	122.92	.00127

The compound $\text{HgClNO}_3 \cdot (\text{C}_3\text{H}_7)_2\text{S}$ melts at $100-102^\circ$. (Found: Hg, 48.008; Cl, 8.32. $\text{HgClNO}_3 \cdot (\text{C}_3\text{H}_7)_2\text{S}$ requires Hg, 48.13 ; Cl, 8.54 per cent.).

The compound $\text{HgClNO}_3 \cdot (\text{C}_4\text{H}_9)_2\text{S}$ melts at 132° . (Found: Hg, 44.73 ; Cl, 7.99. $\text{HgClNO}_3 \cdot (\text{C}_4\text{H}_9)_2\text{S}$ requires Hg, 45.09 ; Cl, 8.004 per cent.).

The reaction of *isobutyl* and *isoamyl* sulphides on silver nitrate was also tried. In the latter case, a thick syrupy liquid was obtained with perceptible evolution of heat. With the former, nothing remarkable happened and the sulphide separated out as an oil. Reaction with phenyl sulphide produced a clay-like amorphous substance.

